

ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION OF UZBEK LEARNERS

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Abstract: the article names two standards and three levels of English pronunciation. The factors necessary for teaching children pronunciation are listed.

Key words: teaching methods, English, pronunciation, child, teacher.

Correct pronunciation is important in learning a foreign language. When teaching children pronunciation, it is important for a teacher to take into account three factors: 1. Due to the fact that language is acquired as a means of communication, work on pronunciation is subordinated to the process of mastering children's speech skills and abilities. The formation of auditory and articulation skills is carried out on those words and patterns of communication that students learn to use in speech at the moment. So, if in the lesson children have to learn the verbs of movement jump, swim, walk, then training is necessary in pronouncing the sounds [w], [d], [u], etc. The sequence of work on phonetic means of communication is determined by the speech units that students use for communication and interaction from lesson to lesson. In order to teach children good pronunciation in English, it is necessary to strive to ensure that from the first lessons and throughout the entire period of training, pronunciation is always in the focus of the teacher: it is necessary to provide children with good training in the perception and pronunciation of sounds.

2. Conscious mastery of pronunciation is based on the characteristics of the sound composition of the English language, taking into account the native language:

1) sounds that are identical in English and Uzbek / Russian, for example: m, b, s, z do not require special training (students master them by transfer);

2) sounds that are somewhat different from similar ones in Uzbek/Russian, such as t, n, d, e, p, k, require correction (children need to be shown how they differ and how they need to be pronounced in order to speak like real English pupils);

3) the third group of sounds, which include sounds not found in the native language [w, h, b, e, g, g, r] also require an explanation of articulation. The conscious orientation of children in pronunciation means of communication will not be complete if the students do not learn to distinguish by ear the difference

in sounds: [i: - I], [u: - u], [b - d], [g - e], [a : - L], [e - I], [n - g], [b - z]. The semantic role of sounds should also be given special attention.

There are three levels of English pronunciation:

Level 1. Often people around do not understand what the student wants to say, because he does not pronounce English words correctly.

Level 2. Others can understand the student, but for this they need to make an effort.

Level 3. The student is easily understood. After all, his pronunciation is clear and pleasant to the ear.

There are two standards for English pronunciation:

- 1) American - General American or GenAm;
- 2) British - Received Pronunciation (RP).

English pronunciation has several main distinguishing features that are inherent in both British and American versions. The sound [d] is significantly different from Russian [d].

In Russian, the front of the tongue is pressed against the inner surface of the upper teeth and gums, and the tip of the tongue is slightly lowered (say the word "house" and track the position of your articulatory apparatus). When pronouncing English [d], the blunt tip of the tongue should be pressed against the alveoli (tubercles above the teeth) at a right angle (try changing the position of the tongue and saying "day"). You will notice that Russian [d] sounded harder than English. This articulation extends to sounds such as [l], [s], [z], [tj], [dʒ], [t], [d], [n]. They are also formed when the tip of the tongue touches the alveoli. In English pronunciation, there is a clear separation of tense and drawn out articulation [1, p. 73]. The order of studying the sounds of the English language is as follows: first, the phonetic sign of the sound that you need to remember is shown in green, then the approximate Russian correspondence to this sound or the sign itself is given in yellow if there is no correspondence to the Russian sound. You need to press the red button and watch the video for this sound; you don't need to understand the video, you need to pay attention only to pronunciation and articulation; video from the British BBC (BBC, not W-W-eS).

The following are examples and voice acting. You don't need to memorize the words, but you can. We pay attention to the letter highlighted in bold, it will give the sound we need. Hovering/clicking on a word will display its transcription. Under the examples there will be additional information on sound that did not fit above.

Pronunciation is important to understand at the beginning of training. It doesn't have to be perfect, just knowing how to do it right and striving for it. There are people who can speak English quickly and a lot, with a high level, etc., but who have not studied pronunciation at all, such people drag this problem at all stages of learning English, and the fact that they speak quickly, you will have to ask them again, because they are not familiar with the correct pronunciation, but they speak their broken English.

That is, some vowel sounds are pronounced quickly, and some are stretched out. In English, the pronunciation of vowels is almost unaffected by consonants. When setting up pronunciation, we recommend combining as many different consonants as possible with a vowel sound. When learning English, due to its special phonetics, it is important in what voice the teacher pronounces words and phrases and what is the expression on his face. Of course, the voice of the teacher should be kind, conducive to communication, and the facial expression should correspond to the tone, which should be trusting, serious, businesslike, expressing the joy of the meeting, and also inspiring success. The main thing is that the student, entering into communication in English, strives with all the means at his disposal to realize this or that communicative intention

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